

Frequency of isolation and molecular characterization of *Clostridium perfringens* toxinotypes in pork carcasses and feces at the slaughterhouse

Carole Feurer^{1*}, Théo Dejaigher¹, Alain Le Roux¹

Ifip-Institut du Porc, Pacé, France

*Corresponding author email: carole.feurer@ifip.asso.fr

Keywords: *Clostridium perfringens*, toxinotypes, pigs, slaughterhouse

BACKGROUND

In France, *C. perfringens* was the 4th pathogen implicated in collective food poisoning outbreaks (FPO) reported in 2022, accounting for 5% of all outbreaks (Santé Publique France, 2024). *C. perfringens* FPOs were associated with meat consumption in 10% of cases (150 FPOs/year). According to the main toxins produced, *C. perfringens* strains are classified into 7 toxinotypes, from A to G. *C. perfringens* strains producing the enterotoxin CPE (toxinotype F) are mainly responsible for food poisoning. Pigs can carry *C. perfringens* in their digestive tract. Meat can thus be contaminated during the slaughtering process, in the event of evisceration incidents. *C. perfringens* prevalence data are lacking in slaughterhouses in France. The aim of the study was to determine the frequency of isolation of *C. perfringens* from carcasses and feces at slaughterhouses, and to characterize the toxinotype of the strains isolated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 150 pigs (30 batches of 5 pigs) from 2 different slaughterhouses were sampled both on their feces (25g) and carcass surfaces (sterile wipes) over an 8-month period. A total of 300 samples were analyzed using an enrichment in IMM (Iron milk medium) broth and streaking on TSC (tryptose-sulfite + cyloserin) plates. characteristic colonies were confirmed in thioglycolate and lactose sulfite broths. Before real-time PCR characterization, the strains were isolated on blood agar to confirm the hemolytic property of *C. Perfringens*.

After DNA extraction using the InstaGene Matrix™ method (Bio-Rad), one strain per positive sample was analyzed by real-time PCR to detect genes encoding the main toxins of *Clostridium perfringens*, according to the method described by Abdelrahim et al., 2019. The genes detected by the method, encoding the main toxins, were: *cpa*, *cpb*, *cpb2*, *etx*, *itx*, *cpe*, and *netB*.

RESULTS

Out of the 300 samples collected, *C. perfringens* was detected in 50 fecal samples and 27 carcass samples. The individual prevalence of *C. perfringens* on feces and carcasses was estimated respectively to be 33.3% [26,3-41,2] and 18,00% [12,7-24,9]. The inter-batch prevalence was 12.00% [7.7-18.1] for feces and 8.00% [4.6-13.5] for carcasses (Table 1). When a batch was positive, the number of positive pigs (feces or carcass) ranged from 1 to 5 (Table 2), confirming the variability of individual contamination within herds already observed for other pathogenic bacteria.

Samples ID	number of samples	Positive pigs	% with CI 95%	Positive batches	% with CI 95%
feces	150	50	33,3% [26,3-41,2]	18	12,00% [7,7-18,1]
Carcasses	150	27	18,00% [12,7-24,9]	12	8,00% [4,6-13,5]

Table 1: Detection frequency of *C. perfringens* on carcasses and in feces

Number of positive pigs	Feces	Carcasses
	Number of batches	Number of batches
1	3	6
2	7	1
3	2	2
4	3	2
5	3	1

Table 2: variability of individual contamination within a herd

Toxinotype A associated with the *cpa* toxin was identified in 98.7% of the 77 characterized strains (50 isolated from feces and 27 from carcasses). One strain showed a Type A associated *cpa* + atypical *cpb2* toxins. No type F *C. perfringens* strains, generally responsible for FPOs, were identified.

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

This study allowed us to obtain the first data on the detection frequency of *C. perfringens* at French slaughterhouses. Data available in the literature mainly concern Asia. In China, for example, 72% (262/364) of fecal samples were tested positive for the presence of *C. perfringens* (Li et al., 2020) and 0.9% to 3.2% of carcasses were positive in Taiwan between 2004 and 2008 (Wang et al., 2013). All strains characterized in this study belonged to toxinotype A, which can cause disease. This is consistent with available worldwide data.

In 20 pigs, we were able to detect the presence of *C. perfringens* both in feces and on the carcass. This suggests that fecal-to-carcass cross-contamination may occur during the slaughtering process. However, strain characterization through typing would be necessary to confirm whether the same strains were isolated from both the feces and the carcass of the same pig. Since pigs carry *C. perfringens* in their digestive tract, the control measures implemented at the slaughterhouse to manage *Salmonella* are also effective against the vegetative forms of *C. perfringens*. However, the spore forms are resistant to singeing temperatures and refrigeration. The application of 1% sodium hypochlorite on surfaces is effective in destroying the spores.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Inaporc, the French national industry association, for their financial support.

REFERENCES

1. Abdelrahim A., M., Radomski N., Delannoy S., Djellal S., Le Négrate M., Hadjab K., Fach P., Hennekinne J. A., Mistou M. Y., Firmesse O. (2019). Large-Scale Genomic Analyses and Toxinotyping of *Clostridium perfringens* Implicated in Foodborne Outbreaks in France, *Frontiers in Microbiology*, Vol 10:777.
2. Li J, Zhou Y, Yang D, Zhang S, Sun Z, Wang Y, Wang S, Wu C. Prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility of *Clostridium perfringens* in chickens and pigs from Beijing and Shanxi, China. *Vet Microbiol.* 2020 Nov 24;252:108932
3. Wang, J-P et al., Pathogenic Microbiological Baseline Survey of Pork Carcasses in Taiwan. 2013. *J Food Prot*, vol 76, Issue 6, 1046-1050.